

Deliverable 8.5: Communication Kit

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

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Declaration: Any work or result described therein is genuinely a result of the Hiperdias project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant

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1 Version History

Version	Summary of Change	Written By	Approver	Date
0.01	Initial draft.	Derek McKenzie	KITE PMs	
0.02	revision	M. Abdou Ahmed	Kite PM's	
1.00	Next Version of Deliverable Report	Derek McKenzie	Kite PM's	16 th March 2018

2 Scope:

The HIPERDIAS Communication Kit has been developed to support the effective dissemination of results and findings within the project. This report has been prepared as an update to Deliverable D8.2. It explains how the communication kit has been used to target all different types of stakeholders, and how it will continue to be used throughout the project.

This document should not be regarded to be a complete or final version. It is intended as a “living” document and as such will evolve throughout the duration of the project. This report will be reviewed by the Consortium and further updated in Deliverable 8.8 (M30).

HIPERDIAS dissemination activities will continue to be monitored throughout the project to compare outputs against the Dissemination Strategy (presented in Deliverable 8.4 & Deliverable 8.7) and to comply with European Commission reporting requirements.

The Communication Kit has been prepared by Kite Innovation (Europe) Ltd (KITE) with the support of the Consortium Partners. KITE will be responsible for the overall co-ordination of the Communication Kit until the proposed GA Amendment is approved resulting in the Termination of Kite and replacement by MODUS Research and Innovation Limited.

Any feedback on this document should be sent to the following people:

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3 Introduction

This document is intended to provide a single point of reference that describes the associated aims and objectives of the Communication Kit and how they will be achieved throughout the lifetime of the project. The Communication Kite content has been designed to be flexible and adaptable to a range of Dissemination requirements. Partners have been encouraged to make recommendations for improvements arising from their utilisation of the various elements of the Kit.

The Consortium recognises the importance of communication within a project and has reviewed in detail the Horizon 2020 guidelines on [‘Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants’](#).

4 Aims and Objectives:

The 'Aims and Objectives' provide direction and a collective sense of purpose for a project. It is difficult for partners to perform in a productive and coordinated manner on a daily/weekly basis without a clear sense of the purpose of their actions. With aims and goals, Work Package leaders can delegate different roles to partners in achieving shared objectives. The Dissemination and Exploitation Work Package encompasses a broad range of activities and is arguably the most diverse of any Work Package as a consequence of that fact all partners are involved on a local, national and international level through a wide variety of channels.

4.1 Aim

The aim of the HIPERDIAS Communication Kit is *'to provide the necessary tools to effectively disseminate results from the project'*.

4.2 Objectives

The Consortium's intentions are to achieve this overall goal by establishing supporting objectives throughout the life of the Project. For the first six months of the Project, the objectives for the communication kit were as listed below:

1. Develop a HIPERDIAS Brochure
2. Develop the 1st Newsletter and circulate to relevant stakeholders
3. Develop future communication tools, depending on the needs of the Consortium.

These primary objectives for the first six months, were superseded by the following objectives:

1. Mobilisation of all partners to make specific commitments to the dissemination of HIPERDIAS
2. Raise awareness of HIPERDIAS at major laser development and laser materials processing events in Europe, North America and Asia
3. Utilisation of Dissemination Kit elements as required to support effective dissemination activity

The dissemination activity is accounted for in Deliverable Report D8.4 Initial Plan for the Use and Dissemination of HIPERDIA results.

5 Communication Kit:

5.1 Communication Kit Research

The foundation for the Communication Kit began with the capture on PINTEREST of all the items that would need to be included within the HIPERDIAS Communication Kit. This comprehensive exercise provided ideas on the content of the Kit and how it would be used to achieve an effective communication approach that was relevant to the project. The HIPERDIAS Communication Kit is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 – HIPERDIAS PINTEREST Board for the Communication Kit.

The HIPERDIAS Project has continued to use PINTEREST to gather ideas and concepts for future dissemination activities e.g. Video Presentations, Social Media ideas and other future Communication activity.

5.2 Presentation Template

A HIPERDIAS presentation template was created to allow partners to disseminate results effectively about the project, as shown in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2 – HIPERDIAS Presentation Template.

This presentation format has been used by all partners to ensure that the Project is being publicised in a consistent manner and to establish the HIPERDIAS brand in the minds of all Stakeholders. The template correctly acknowledges the European Commission and Photonics 21 as it is required to do and has been extensively used at events detailed in Deliverable Report D8.4.

5.3 Flyer

Printed leaflets and flyers are an inexpensive way of advertising the HIPERDIAS Project to potential stakeholders. The consortium has created a version that provides an overview of the project, as well as its aims, objectives and targets, as shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3 – HIPERDIAS Flyer (Version 1)

Partners are disseminating the flyers at meetings, Conferences and other activities that present an opportunity to raise awareness of the project. Sending flyers onto contacts encountered at meetings is also a good follow-up tactic that the partners have been deployed. The flyers have been well-received by the recipients.

5.4 Newsletter Template

The Newsletter Template provides a well-designed format for the development of subsequent Newsletters that will feature during the duration of the Project, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – Newsletter Template (Version 0.01) This is an example only

The Project Newsletter is prepared on a yearly basis for distribution to relevant stakeholders and is coordinated by Kite Innovation (Europe) Ltd.

6 Future development of the Communication Kit

Partner consultations take place at each Consortium Meeting as a means of identifying potential ways of improving the Communication Kit. It is acknowledged that successful implementation of the Communication Kit also hinges on the combined efforts of all consortium members.

Partners are required to continue inform the project management team when disseminating any activities related to the Project, which might include:

- Project Results
- Attendance of Conferences
- & also images of Partners disseminating their Project Results.

This continues to generate rich data and content from which the consortium will select the best items to be disseminated.

2018 also represents a significant opportunity for the consortium and the dissemination activity as the Research and Technical Development (RTD) of the project matures and delivers concrete results in terms of high power lasers for evaluation in the targeted application areas:

- Element Six with Class 4 Lasers evaluating the 200W laser in processing of diamond
- Bosch with LASEA evaluating the 500W Laser machine in the 3D processing of silicon
- Class 4 Lasers evaluating the 200W laser in the fine cutting of metals

The dissemination activity can be expected to ramp upwards as these results put substance into the presentation activity of the project partners. We believe the Communication Kit is fit for purpose to support this but this will be reviewed as and when feedback suggests that new or enhanced elements are needed in the Kit to support the partners. Ultimately the project partners expect that the demonstration of 1Kw laser processing will be achieved in relevant applications and this will constitute a major opportunity for dissemination activity on the back of a significant result.

The existence of 3 different application areas provides a lot of scope to generate newsworthy content as the laser materials processing strategies are developed and honed with the new laser capability available in the project. Whilst it is un-realistic to expect that all the evaluation data generated will become the subject of dissemination activity, we expect the output of the evaluation work to produce the following outcomes:

- Process results that are the subject of confidential IP or know-how that will not be divulged
- Positive process results that can be presented without compromising the IP protection of the data
- Process results that reveal limitations of the processing strategies and/or the laser machine capability or new information about the processing of the targeted materials.

The management team continue to remind the Partners of their responsibilities to disseminate and are reminded of this during the Teleconferences and Consortium Meetings.

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